

LIFESTYLE OF STUDENTS AND ITS EFFECT ON HEALTH

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Abstract. *It is known that the state of health is reflected in all spheres of human life. The completeness and intensity of the various aspects of human life depends on the level of health, its qualitative characteristics, which in a certain sense determine the way of life and lifestyle of a person. At the same time, there is an inverse relationship here: the student's lifestyle, the level and nature of his activity in life, especially in work, largely determine his health status.*

Keywords: *lifestyle, students, effect, aspect, activity, health.*

Relevance. Such interdependence creates great opportunities for prevention and health promotion. Health affects the quality of labor resources, production efficiency, and thus the dynamics of economic development of society. The level of health and physical development is one of the important conditions for the quality of the workforce. Depending on these indicators, the possibilities of human participation in various fields of labor activity are evaluated in 69 ways. Therefore, at the stage of choosing a specialty and vocational training, the problem of a person's suitability for specific types of professional activity is objectively resolved. Health of students is one of the important social problems of the society. Successful training of highly qualified personnel is directly related to strengthening and protection of health, increasing the working capacity of the growing students. In modern conditions, this group of children is more exposed to the negative influence of the external environment, because their sexual and physical formation corresponds to the period of adaptation to new, changed living conditions, high mental loads. Maintaining and strengthening the health of students is mainly determined by the lifestyle. High attention to it is manifested at the level of society's consciousness, in the field of culture, education, upbringing. The composition of life style is shown in the relations of subordination and coordination, which are different manifestations of life activity. If the style of haèt does not include creative types of haèt activity, then its level will decrease. Some students use their free time to study, others to exercise, and still others to socialize. With conscious planning of time and energy, the student can join or separate from a wide network of such connections. Students of higher education institutions form a stratum of the population united by a certain age, specific conditions of study and lifestyle. 17-20-year-olds form the basis of the first courses in higher educational institutions. For most of the students, the first years of study at the institute coincide with adolescence, and during this period the process of formation of the organism and the final formation of the personality is still going on. The peculiarity of this state is that the formation of the cardiovascular and other systems of the body, as well as separate structures of the brain and higher neuropsychological functions is not completed, and, accordingly, it is observed that they are highly variable and sensitive [5]. A student's lifestyle cannot be influenced from outside. A person has real opportunities to choose the forms of life activity, types of behavior that are important for him. The analysis of the concrete materials of the students' life activity shows that it is disorderly and chaotically organized [4,5]. This condition is reflected in not taking food on

time, regularly sleeping less, not being in the fresh air, not exercising enough, lack of exercise treatments, doing independent studies at 70 sleep time, smoking and other similar important factors. At the same time, the impact of individual factors of students' lifestyle, which is considered 100%, is extremely important. For example, 24-30% corresponds to sleep mode, 10-16% to eating mode, 15-30% to movement activity. During the academic year, the negative consequences of organizing such life activities in this way accumulate, and by the time of its end, it becomes the most obvious example (the number of diseases increases). Since these processes are repeated during 5-6 years of study, they have a significant impact on the health of students. Special studies have shown that if the student's health level is taken as 100% in the 1st year, then in the 2nd year their health has decreased to 91.9%, in the 3rd year to 83.1%, and in the 4th year to -75.8% [4]. These data indicate that the practical exercises on physical education carried out in higher educational institutions cannot automatically guarantee the maintenance and strengthening of students' health. [1,2]. It is provided by many aspects of the lifestyle, among them physical exercise, regular participation in sports, and health factors occupy an important place. In recent years, the attention of students to a healthy lifestyle has become more active. A healthy lifestyle creates such a socio-cultural microenvironment for a person that in such conditions a basis is created for highly creative spending of energy, work ability, work and public activity, psychological comfort, and the psychophysiological possibilities of a person are more fully opened. The process of his self-improvement becomes relevant, responsibility for health in the conditions of a healthy lifestyle is formed in students as a part of general cultural development [3]. The content of the healthy lifestyle of students reflects the result of the spread of personal and group behavior, communication, and the method of organizing life activities, strengthened to the traditional style. The main elements of a healthy lifestyle are the following: work and rest, eating and sleeping patterns, compliance with hygienic requirements, organization of an individual purpose-oriented order of movement activity, throwing away harmful habits, interpersonal communication and culture of behavior in the team. A student with a high level of personality development is characterized not only by the desire for self-realization, but also the desire to change himself, to change the microenvironment in which he lives. A person's lifestyle is formed through active self-change [2]. The influence of the external environment on the level of health is also important. Currently, a large amount of scientific material has been collected that proves the direct impact of a number of factors of the external environment (climate, weather, ecological situation) on human health. Environmental conditions also affect human health. Disturbance of the ecological balance may cause the risk of failure of human adaptation mechanisms. The body is exposed to the negative effects of physical radiation with various disorders; with occupational diseases related to new professions; with nervous and mental instability to informational loads; responds to changes in the chemical composition of the external environment with allergic reactions. Students are a social stratum of the population that can be included in the high-risk group, because students have unusual social problems (adaptation to physiological and anatomical changes associated with the formation process; high psycho-emotional and mental load, getting used to new conditions of living and studying; interpersonal relationships outside the family formation) can affect their formation in society.

Conclusions. An important element of a healthy lifestyle is personal hygiene. It includes a rational daily routine, body care, hygiene of clothes and clothes. The agenda is also important.

When it is followed correctly, a specific rhythm of the body's work is developed. This, in turn, creates better conditions for studying and recovery. It is necessary to pay special attention to sleep. Regular lack of full sleep can cause exhaustion of the nervous system, weakening of the body's defenses, reduced work capacity, and deterioration of self-esteem.

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